

IMPLICATING TASK-BASED LEARNING IN TEACHING LEGAL ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation aims to examine the role of task-based learning in teaching and learning legal English. The triangulated data showed that the appropriateness of the tasks in the classes plays a crucial role to get the students to be engaged in what they are doing and learning. The dichotomy between modern and traditional approaches with regards to teach legal English will have an elaborate investigation in this paper through applying in authentic experimental teaching process.

INTRODUCTION

A discussion has arisen in recent years about which approaches of designing, planning, and implementing classes are more effective. The advantages of a task-based learning method (TBL) over the more traditional Present, Practice, Produce (PPP) technique are discussed in this article. To begin, the teacher places a piece of language in a clear context to convey its meaning. This could be accomplished in a number of ways, including through a text, a situation build, or a chat. Students are then asked to undergo a controlled practice stage in which they may be required to repeat target elements through choral and individual drilling, fill in gaps, or match half-sentence halves. All of this practice necessitates the student's right usage of the language and assists them in becoming more comfortable with it. There are some difficulties with PPP.

All of this seems reasonable, but teachers who follow this strategy will quickly notice flaws:

Students might convey the impression of being comfortable with the new language by accurately generating it in class. However, after a few courses, students will frequently be unable to generate the language correctly, if not at all.

Students will frequently produce the language, but will abuse the goal structure to the point that it sounds artificial. Students may not produce the target language during free practice because they are able to perform the assignment using current language resources.

A task-based strategy

Language teachers can use task-based learning as an alternative. In a task-

based lesson, the teacher does not decide which language will be studied ahead of time; instead, the session is built around the completion of a primary task, and the language studied is chosen by what happens as pupils complete it. The lesson is divided into stages.

- Pre-task
- Task
- Planning
- Report
- Analysis
- Practice

A TBL's Benefits Task-based learning has a number of distinct advantages. The pupils have no language control, unlike in a PPP method. They must employ all of their language resources in all three levels, rather than just practicing one pre-selected item. The students' experiences with the language, which is individualized and meaningful to them, are used to create a natural environment. PPP requires the creation of situations in which to display the language, which can be somewhat odd at times. With TBL, the students will be exposed to a considerably wider range of languages. They will be introduced to a variety of lexical phrases, collocations, patterns, and language forms. The language studied is based on the needs of the students. Rather than a decision made by the teacher or the coursebook, this need decides what will be covered in the session. It is a communicative technique in which pupils spend a lot of time talking to one another. In comparison, PPP lessons appear to be more teacher-centered. During a task-based class, keep an eye on how much time

the students spend communicating. It is entertaining and motivational.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The popularity of Task-Based Learning (TBL) has recently prompted numerous scholars, instructors, and methodologists to assess the approach's efficacy. Despite the fact that it has been in use for a long time, its popularity has grown. One of the key drivers of this interest is educators' aim to encourage true communication, or the sharing of meanings, rather than just forms. Another reason for this interest is that practitioners believe that pupils learn better languages when they are not solely focused on linguistic forms. Researchers feel that if language form is not a priority, there is less anxiety and learning is more successful. Language acquisition becomes more relevant and natural when task-based training is used. Currently, the assignment is thought to be the most effective way to promote second language acquisition (SLA) in the classroom. "Engaging learners in task work provides a better setting for the activation of learning processes," say Richards and Rodgers (2004). (p. 223). TBL's meaning negotiation, according to these writers, offers the input and output required for language acquisition. When it comes to defining a task, there is no universal definition. Here are some examples of how "task" has been defined by experts in the subject. If task-based instruction takes place, language learning is more meaningful and natural. The task is currently considered to be the most effective means of promoting second language acquisition (SLA) in the classroom. According to Richards and Rodgers (2004), "engaging learners in task work provides a

better context for the activation of learning processes" (p. 223). The authors say the negotiation of meaning in TBL provides the input and output necessary for language acquisition. If one wants to define a task, there is not a single definition. Here are some examples of how individuals in the field have characterized "task".

A task, according to Nunan (1989), is "a piece of classroom work in which learners comprehend, manipulate, produce, or interact in the target language while their attention is largely focused on meaning rather than form" (p. 10). According to this definition, students will employ prior knowledge to attain their goal; if new information is required (for example, linguistic forms or vocabulary), the instructor will function as a knower and supply it so that students do not disrupt the process and reach the desired result. A task, according to Willis (1996), is an action "in which the learner uses the target language for a communicative purpose (goal) in order to obtain an outcome" (p. 23). A meaning-based approach is more effective than a form-based one. Even if some of the vocabulary is incorrect, students express themselves. Skehan (1996) adds that tasks are primarily focused on meaning and mimic real-life circumstances in this regard. Participants choose the language forms to utilize to attain the goal since tasks are goal-directed activities. Van den Branden (2006) discusses how tasks have been employed in second language research to explore language production, interaction, and meaning negotiation - all facets of second language acquisition (SLA). A task, according to this source, is "an action that a person engages in in order to achieve a

purpose and that necessitates the use of words" (p. 4).

It is clear from this description that a language form is required to complete a work; yet, the language is merely a means to a goal. When dealing with real-life communicative situations, language is the vehicle to use to achieve successful communication. The most popular and widely accepted definition of task nowadays is that it is a verbal action with an emphasis on meaning. Task-Based Learning is a strategy that demands teachers to create lessons, not just class activities, in order to facilitate actual dialogue. All of the definitions above agree that tasks are goal-oriented and meaning-centered activities; tasks are created to make it easier for students to participate in meaningful activities. Language entails communication, and this communication can only take place when the context allows for the exchange of genuine and meaningful thoughts. Some of the variations stem from the fact that a job might have many purposes depending on the needs of the students and teachers. Despite the fact that TBL focuses on meaning, it does not ignore form. Each task model has a period in class dedicated to focusing on form, which is distinct from focusing on language, as detailed later in this paper. Willis and Willis (2007), for example, concentrate on forms at the end of each task cycle, which is defined as a set of tasks that are related to one another. At the end of each job sequence, there are three reasons to concentrate on language form.

Firstly, learners comprehend language in its context. Students will surely prepare and use language while completing the activity. Second, rather than focusing on language

form, students concentrate on language use. Throughout the cycle, each activity has a unique purpose and quality that draws students' attention and interest in the language that will be required to complete the goal task. Finally, students are introduced to the creation and reception of language. Learners participate in real-world tasks that require them to talk, write, and understand through listening and reading. Teachers do not have to correct every error in order for effective communication to occur. Teachers should view language as a tool rather than a goal, which implies that mistakes are a natural part of the learning process and not always the result of poor learning or instruction. As a result, meaningful tasks imply meaningful learning, and meaningful communication is the culmination of meaningful tasks. Similarly, the circumstances in which a work is completed will have a significant impact on the sort of language used by learners in communicative activities.

When Ellis (2003) claims that Task-Based Learning and Teaching requires classroom participants to forget they are in a teaching-learning setting and envisage themselves in a more communicatively effective environment where meaning negotiation is taking place, he is referring to this circumstance. The explanation for this appears to be self-evident: the purpose of language instruction is (or should be) to enable students to convey personal meanings. Certain scholars, like as Long (1983), emphasize the importance of including meaning negotiation in a task in order to effectively advance language acquisition. As a result, it is said, we should give our students meaningful work with

plenty of opportunity for meaning negotiation. Roles of the teacher and students in task-based learning. Within a task-based approach, the roles of the teacher and pupils alter. Learning and teaching are viewed as collaborative endeavors in TBL. The focus of the classes is on the students. By becoming facilitators, teachers address students' needs and interests. Teachers who engage in Task-Based Learning, according to Willis and Willis (2007), promote real language use by becoming discussion leaders and organizers, managers of group or pair work, motivators to engage students in performing a task, and language experts to provide language feedback when needed. The key issues are the extents to which the teacher is in charge of material.

METHODOLOGY

The present paper illuminates following steps:

Step I – collecting theoretical data

In the initial stage of the experimental process, the researcher pursued the matter of task-based learning through perusing articles, journals and scientific papers investigated by linguists so that she could assemble germane data in support of the empirical study. The foundations of the research plan were laid by exploring different sources of information in order to accomplish best of the outcomes in further development of educational syllabi.

Step II – conducting interviews

The researcher clarified the perspectives of the teachers' on the application of the task-based learning strategies with the help of the purposefully designed questions for the interview for the teachers which would help the investigator to determine the key factors needed to be taken into consideration in teaching Legal English. Further, they clarified the role of effective learning strategies in learning target language effectively according to the responses of the subjects.

Step III – teaching process

The proceeding stage of the research is considered to be commencing the actual experimental process which included a two-month time frame lasting from first of September till December. Each group took part in the research process; the first group 'M' received all instructional delivery through task-based learning approaches while the second group 'T' were exposed to traditional approaches this was to sift the novelty of suggested teaching practice. To start with the experimental lessons, the respondents were allocated with Needs Analysis with the aim of identifying individuals' beliefs on varied language input and cognitive factors that may influence in second language acquisition. The participants of two groups, experimental and control, were delivered with different instructional delivery. The former was taught applying variety of the learning strategies while the latter received only explanation of the rules and do the exercises to strengthen their knowledge. The researcher struggled hard to integrate all language teaching methods over the experimental process in order to analyze specifications of the strategies in fostering

speaking skills. After having been explained rules the students performed different tasks on the base of the learned strategies.

Step IV – conducting post-test

In final stage of the research, the researcher distributed post-tests to validate the practicality and actuality of the research paper by involving participants to perform different tests that challenged their brain to perform their abilities in each learned method. The researcher put special considerations to the final implications of the research so there were excluded minor points so that learners would find solutions themselves later while carrying out post-tests.

The last step was examining and establishing the results in order to validate the credibility of the experimental lessons that focused on examining involvement of varied language input in teaching target language.

Research questions

In attaining more successful outcomes of the experiment, chief considerations were given to the following points:

- Does the task-based learning have an impact on learning Legal English?
- To what extend will students be more competent if they can expand their exposure to task-based learning?

Research participants

The sample for the study was selected from the second-year students of Tashkent State University of Law. The participants comprised of twenty upper-intermediate learners with equal divisions

in two groups. Majority of the participants were 19-year-old EFL learners who had fairly well operational command in English. The groups were assigned as groups 'M' and 'T' in accordance with the initials of the instructional delivery (Modern and Traditional approaches) they would be receiving during the experimental period. Nearly one third of the participants had been involved in active task-based learning in their Legal English classes. The respondents of the study consisted of a fairly equal amount of both genders, however, girls dominated over boys accounting for 61% and 49% respectively. In accomplishing better outcomes, the views of each sex were taken into account in this current paper.

Analysis of the data

Throughout the research three types of data were collected. First of all, the researcher gathered the opinions of teachers on how they implement task-based learning into the classroom. The interview with the students helped to collect the data which tell students' opinions and how task-based learning helped them in learning legal terms in English. Further, they analyze students' hardships that challenge them most while mastering competent speaking skills. This data helped the researcher to know about the learners' level and their motives which were of the greatest essence to improve the quality of the lesson by taking into account learners' specific interests and needs. Finally, the last type of data was gathered during the study according to the results of pre and post test results of the students which indicated accurate measurements of their abilities in dealing with legal English.

Pre-tests

At the beginning of the study, the researcher took a sample of pre-test in order to clarify the students' overall awareness concerning the level of their language proficiency. The learners were distributed a handout with different tasks. There were a multiple-choice and true/false question types with pictures on the handout. While they were undertaking the task, she observed what modes of learning strategies were being used. Furthermore, she asked the students to be able to predict some words and not to lose concentration at the most.

Process

After the accomplishment of the test, it was clear that the learners have many problems with handling the difficult tasks of the language and that could be very good chance to sort out the tasks which would be helpful for the students. Over the course of conducting the experimental lessons, the researcher put a stress on using those tasks to improve their overall achievement in language proficiency as well as legal English which would itself facilitate the researcher to reach intended goals.

Post- tests

In the post test, the researcher chose the rating from 25 to 30 score scale as an evaluation system for participants' involvement in the experiment. Then, the researcher compared the results of the pre and post-test in order to validate the reliability of the suggested teaching methods whether they improved their legal English or not. This was the exclusive research tool to ascertain the actuality and reliability of the research paper by giving

relevant comparisons on the overall achievements of the subjects. The process of data collection was successfully finished. The researcher gathered all the information and began analyzing them. All the collected data were used to determine the efficacy of the teaching process. Every fact was carefully learned.

FINDINGS

The findings of the study revealed that to teach EFL learners through task-based learning in legal English classes has beneficial effects in their academic progress. According to the data reported in questionnaires it can be concluded that students have differing attitudes towards the application of tasks related to the topic they are learning in the classrooms. The chief considerations in selecting the groups were based on the implications of the conducted surveys that focused on appraising individuals' preference on two types of the approaches: modern and traditional.

The results of the study also show that acquisition process of the students has been improved as a result of the practice and tasks they are engaged in. Majority of the students claimed that the experimental lessons they had been exposed to was very helpful in terms of selecting appropriate learning strategies for themselves. Also, they affirmed that being introduced with current teaching practice they discovered new encouraging motivational initiatives to foster their spoken output.

The final implications of the study disclosed that a vast amount of the participants approved the idea of

implementing appropriate tasks in language classes owing to the wide range of advantages they offer to the students. They urged to pay attention to the fact that mastery of native like fluency and speech production could be achieved easily once they were introduced with authentic speaking materials, for instance, movies that are really helpful in enhancing both speaking skills and legal English. The special considerations of the study took into account familiarizing students with cultural background of target language so that they would not encounter with misunderstandings related with cultural issues.

CONCLUSION

Choosing appropriate tasks in legal English context is a difficult task. It requires more attention of teachers and regular practice of speaking skill inside or outside the classroom. The research findings helped to clarify some essential conclusions both for the language educators and EFL learners. Furthermore, it was much clear from the contrast between pre-tests and post tests taken from the subjects. The final indications of them facilitated the researcher to make relevant comparisons in support of the research questions. The actual achievements of the subjects could be examined exclusively with the help of the data presented in these assessment tools. So, the ultimate aim of this study was to show whether it is possible to develop students' legal English vocabulary through the use of effective tasks. It was shown that using different effective tasks, learners can develop their speaking skill, reduce their problems in understanding the incoming messages and have the chance to correct

their pronunciation of certain words. Moreover, they can learn new words, vocabulary and more than that speak fluently. The analysis of second-year students' pre- and post- tests' results

showed that the learners have chances to improve their speaking through the use of as effective tools in providing the real speech.

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